

Role of IL-13 in allergic rhinitis inflammation: Preliminary results^{*}

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Abstract

Allergic rhinitis (AR) is a major public health problem with a growing global prevalence, currently affecting approximately 30% of the world population. There remains limited understanding of how local cytokine production patterns following nasal allergen challenge relate to clinical symptoms, particularly in the context of the late-phase allergic response.

Interleukin-13 (IL-13) has emerged as a significant contributor to the development of allergic inflammation in recent years. It shares many functional features with interleukin-4 (IL-4) due to the presence of a common receptor subunit. Although findings in the literature remain conflicting, they consistently support the role of IL-13 as a primary cause of allergic inflammation. The *IL13* gene is expressed at higher levels in the nasal mucosa of both humans and mouse models with allergic rhinitis; however, the exact role of IL-13 in AR pathogenesis remains unclear. The present study aimed to investigate IL-13 expression levels in patients with clinically confirmed allergic rhinitis and demonstrate that increased expression levels of IL-13 gene products (protein and mRNA) play a critical role in disease development and immune activation, potentially serving as a diagnostic and therapeutic biomarker.

In recent years, IL-13 has emerged as a key mediator in the pathology of allergic inflammation. It shares numerous functional properties with IL-4, owing to their use of a common receptor subunit. While literature findings vary, they consistently support the role of IL-13 as a key driver of allergic inflammation.

Keywords

airway hypersensitivity, allergic rhinitis, IL-13, inflammation, interleukin-13, Th2 cytokines

Introduction

Allergic rhinitis (AR) is characterized by symptoms such as nasal congestion, clear rhinorrhea, sneezing, postnasal drip, and nasal itching. Historically considered a disease confined to the nasal airways, AR is now classified as a

type I hypersensitivity disorder involving rapid IgE-mediated immune responses, as supported by the united airway theory (Jeffery and Haahtela 2006; Bousquet et al. 2008; Aguilar et al. 2023). AR can be classified as intermittent (seasonal) or chronic (perennial), with approximately 20% of cases being seasonal, 40% perennial, and

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the remaining 40% showing mixed characteristics (Skoner 2001). Approximately 80% of AR symptoms manifest before the age of 20, with a peak between 35 and 40 years (Nur Husna et al. 2022). According to the World Allergy Organization (<https://www.worldallergy.org>), AR affects over 400 million people worldwide. In the United States, between 10 and 30% of adults and up to 40% of children aged 10–18 years are affected, making AR the fifth most common chronic condition. In Europe and China, prevalence rates are estimated at 11% and 10–13%, respectively (Hastan et al. 2011).

Symptoms, both nasal and extra-nasal, can persist for hours after allergen exposure, particularly with prolonged allergen contact (Wheatley and Togias 2015). This prolonged exposure leads to mucosal hyperresponsiveness not only to the allergen itself but also to other allergic and non-allergic stimuli such as strong odors or irritants (Justiz Vaillant and Zito 2018; Valenta et al. 2018). Diagnostic criteria incorporate recommendations from the Global Initiative for Asthma (Global Asthma Network 2014) and the ARIA (Allergic Rhinitis and Its Impact on Asthma) guidelines – an international collaboration with the World Health Organization (WHO) through the Global Alliance against Chronic Respiratory Diseases (GARD) (Bousquet et al. 2008).

As it is difficult to determine with absolute precision the exact proportion of the population affected by AR, it is equally challenging to quantify the disease's impact at both the individual and population levels. A 2021 study (Roland et al. 2021) utilized the Truven Health Analytics MarketScan database, which includes health insurance claims covering approximately 50% of the U.S. population (Kulaylat et al. 2019). The authors found that approximately 30% of the population had rhinitis, yet only 12.3% of these individuals sought medical care. Annual costs for consultations, diagnostics, and medications exceeded \$4.6 billion. A 2016 study in Sweden concluded that AR costs the Swedish economy approximately €1.3 billion, primarily due to reduced work productivity (Cardell et al. 2016), while the estimated burden in the Netherlands reaches around €20 billion (Avdeeva et al. 2020).

Pathophysiology of allergic rhinitis and the role of IL-13

The causes of AR and other allergic disorders are complex. It is generally recognized that genetic and environmental factors, including immunological components, play significant roles in the development of AR. Additionally, specific epigenetic modifications may contribute to the onset and progression of allergic conditions. Type I hypersensitivity is an IgE-mediated response to allergens (Wheatley and Togias 2015). These reactions occur rapidly, typically within 20 minutes of contact with allergens. They are characterized by the activation and infiltration of mast cells and other inflammatory cells into the affected tissues (Gangwar et al. 2016). Dendritic cells and other antigen-presenting cells capture allergens at the mucosal surface, process them, and present antigenic peptides on ma-

yor histocompatibility complex (MHC) class II molecules. This antigen–MHC complex binds to T-cell receptors on naïve CD4⁺ T cells, causing them to differentiate into Th2 cells. When Th2 cells are activated, they release cytokines such as interleukin-4 (IL-4) and interleukin-13 (IL-13), which work in conjunction with B cells to produce IgE antibodies specific to allergens. These antibodies attach to high-affinity IgE receptors (FcεRI) on mast cells, resulting in their activation (He et al. 2015; Finkelman et al. 2016; Tan et al. 2016; Sani et al. 2019; Nur Husna et al. 2022). The mediators released cause mucosal edema and rhinorrhea, two of the most common symptoms of AR. About 4 to 6 hours after exposure, the late-phase allergic reaction begins. This occurs when the nasal mucosa remains inflamed and various immune cells, including T cells, eosinophils, neutrophils, basophils, and monocytes, are recruited (Sin and Togias 2011). Cytokines such as IL-4 and IL-5 cause this influx of cells by increasing the expression of adhesion molecules on endothelial cells, facilitating immune cell migration to the inflamed tissue (Pawankar 2000).

The complex interplay between the respiratory epithelium and the immune system serves a protective role in healthy individuals by preventing the penetration of foreign particles and pathogens across the epithelial barrier (Johnston et al. 2021). Allergen exposure triggers cytokine production in various combinations, and recent studies have revealed that distinct interleukins play specific roles in the pathogenesis of allergic diseases (Nakajima and Takatsu 2007; Bayrak Dergimenci et al. 2018; Golebski et al. 2021; Wang et al. 2023).

The global prevalence of AR and asthma is increasing rapidly (Bousquet et al. 2008). These conditions frequently co-occur and often share genetic risk variants associated with immune-related genes (Ober and Yao 2011; Ferreira et al. 2014). Both diseases are mediated by Th2-immunological responses, in which Th2 cytokines such as IL-3, IL-4, IL-5, and IL-13 play central roles in disease development (Vlaykov et al. 2020; Nur Husna et al. 2022). IL-4 promotes the differentiation of myeloid dendritic cells (MDCs) and facilitates the migration of Th2 cells and eosinophils to the site of inflammation. IL-13 stimulates B cells to produce IgE, induces goblet cell hyperplasia, promotes airway hyperresponsiveness, and enhances mucus hypersecretion (Sahoo et al. 2016).

The chromosomal region 5q31.1 has been extensively investigated, as it contains several candidate genes for allergic diseases, including those encoding the Th2 cytokines IL-4 and IL-13 (Giuffrida et al. 2019). In allergic rhinitis, the Th2 response predominantly involves T cells infiltrating the nasal mucosa and secreting IL-13, which significantly contributes to IgE-mediated allergic inflammation (Pawankar et al. 2014). Together with IL-4, IL-13 promotes the differentiation of T cells toward a Th2 phenotype and enhances the capacity of B cells. Additionally, IL-13 shares many biological activities with IL-4 and plays a critical role in the allergic response by mediating class switch recombination to IgE (Shirkani et al. 2019). In patients with perennial allergic rhinitis or following nasal allergen provocation, *IL13* gene expression is elevated in the nasal mucosa (Pawankar et al. 1995).

The role of IL-13 in the early and late phases of allergic rhinitis remains incompletely defined. Multiple immune cell populations produce IL-13 (Joshi et al. 2006; Giuffrida et al. 2019), and this cytokine induces functional alterations in epithelial and smooth muscle cells, leading to hypersensitivity reactions (Ito et al. 2009). Data indicate that elevated and abnormally high levels of IL-13 and other cytokines contribute to disease progression, exacerbation, and chronicity (Yu et al. 2019; Nur Husna et al. 2022).

Materials and methods

Subject criteria and characteristics

The present study included 20 patients aged between 18 and 55 years and 20 healthy controls matched for age, regardless of gender. The inclusion criteria for patients were (1) age ≥ 18 years, non-smokers for the past year; (2) diagnosis of upper airway diseases (moderate/severe allergic rhinitis [AR] or seasonal/perennial AR); (3) rhinosinusitis based on EPOS classification, sensitization to inhalant allergens (grass and tree pollens, house dust mites, pet dander, and molds); (4) no specific immunotherapy in the past 3 years; and (5) no use of nasal or oral corticosteroids or antihistamines in the last 6 months.

Patients were retrospectively selected from a large database and were part of a national study. They had been hospitalized at the Clinic of Allergology, University Hospital “Alexandrovska,” between December 2017 and December 2020. All participants were volunteers with a clinical history of hay fever.

Each participant signed an informed consent form and completed a questionnaire detailing medical history, lifestyle and physical activity, medication and supplement intake, harmful habits, and frequency of disease exacerbation.

The table below summarizes the distribution and clinical characteristics of the patients and healthy controls.

Table 1. Clinical and demographic characteristics of the study subjects.

	AR Patients (n = 20)	Healthy Controls (n = 20)
Age (years)	29.8 \pm 5.7	31.82 \pm 7.55
Male	7 (35%)	10 (50%)
Female	13 (65%)	10 (50%)
Family history of AR		
- Yes (%)	5 (25%)	0 (0%)
- No (%)	15 (75%)	20 (100%)
Clinical form of AR		
- Seasonal	10 (50%)	-
- Perennial	7 (35%)	-
- Exacerbated	3 (25%)	-
Disease duration		
- >1 year	15 (75%)	-
- <1 year	5 (25%)	-

AR – allergic rhinitis.

There was a slight predominance of females among the patients, but gender distribution was not considered a variable in the study.

Pulmonary function assessment was performed using spirometry, and the results are shown in Table 2. Minor

Table 2. Pulmonary function test results in the two groups.

	FVC	FEV1	FEV1/ FVC	FEF25- 75	FEF25	FEF50	PEF
AR patients	98.23 \pm 7.78	100.8 \pm 10.57	104.27 \pm 8.04	101.41 \pm 27.03	94.31 \pm 35.33	98.52 \pm 26.81	99.15 \pm 20.28
Healthy Controls	93.20 \pm 6.87	86.20 \pm 15.97	95.60 \pm 12.05	68.00 \pm 32.15	80.40 \pm 20.04	69.60 \pm 32.71	83.60 \pm 7.47

differences were observed between the groups in FEV₁ (100.8 \pm 10.57 vs. 86.20 \pm 15.97) and FEF_{25–75} (94.31 \pm 35.33 vs. 68.00 \pm 32.15).

Biological samples collected

Biological material included serum samples and nasal lavage. Serum was obtained from venous blood collected in non-EDTA tubes. Samples were centrifuged at 12,000 rpm for 15 minutes and then transferred to clean tubes, after which they were stored at -80°C . Nasal lavage was collected by instilling isotonic saline into both nostrils, followed by the subject expelling the fluid into a sterile container after 10 seconds. The samples were centrifuged at 1,200 rpm for 15 minutes and stored at -80°C .

Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA)

Serum and nasal lavage interleukin-13 (IL-13) levels were quantified using the Human IL-13 ELISA kit (Gene Probe, Diaclone, France) according to the manufacturer's instructions. The method is a sandwich ELISA designed for in vitro quantification of cytokines in biological samples. The microplate wells were pre-coated with a highly specific antibody against IL-13.

During the first incubation, any IL-13 present in the sample bound to the immobilized antibodies. Spectrophotometric detection was performed using the Tecan Spark 2100 reader at 450/630 nm with PGM software, employing six standards and a blank. The intensity of the color reaction was directly proportional to the concentration of cytokine in the biological sample. A standard curve was constructed based on the calibrators, and cytokine levels were determined from the curve.

Real-time polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR)

Total RNA was isolated using the QIAamp RNA Blood Mini Kit (QIAGEN) according to the manufacturer's protocol. Nucleic acids were eluted in 30 μL of AVE elution buffer provided in the kit. This kit is designed for high-purity isolation of nucleic acids from various

biological samples, including blood, sputum, plasma, urine, and serum. RNA concentrations were evaluated using the Harvard Bioscience BioDrop DUO UV/Vis spectrophotometer.

Real-time polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) was employed to assess the transcriptional levels of *IL13*. The kit used was KiCqStart SYBR Green qPCR ReadyMix (Sigma-Aldrich, Merck), which includes all necessary reagents for reverse transcription.

Amplification and analysis were conducted on a Rotor-Gene Q 2plex (QIAGEN), a rotary-based instrument with dual detection channels. Detection relied on the amplification of *IL13* gene sequences using specifically designed primers sourced from the literature (Chu et al. 2016). The housekeeping gene *GAPDH* (glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase) served as an internal control.

A negative control was included, containing all reaction components except the RNA template. Thermal cycling conditions were as follows: an initial denaturation at 95 °C for 5 minutes, followed by 37 cycles of denaturation at 95 °C for 10 seconds, primer annealing at 55 °C for 35 seconds, and extension at 72 °C for 35 seconds. A final elongation step was performed at 72 °C for 3 minutes. All samples were run in triplicate. Normalized gene expression was analyzed using REST 2009 V2.0.13 (QIAGEN).

Expression differences were determined based on Ct value variations. Results were presented as fold change in expression relative to the control group. Relative expression levels were calculated using the $2^{-\Delta\Delta Ct}$ method (Schmittgen and Livak 2008).

Statistical analysis

Statistical methods included both descriptive and inferential analyses. ELISA data were processed using SPSS for Windows 13.0 (IBM SPSS Statistics) and GraphPad Prism 8. Results were reported as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) for each variable.

RT-PCR data were statistically analyzed using REST 2009 V2.0.13 (QIAGEN). Significant differences were indicated with p-values. Error bars in the figures represent the standard error of the mean (SEM) or the standard deviation (SD).

Results and discussion

Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) analysis of IL-13 in nasal lavage and serum samples from patients with AR and healthy controls

Various methods have been developed for detecting and quantifying specific proteins in biological samples. The enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) is a technique analogous to immunoblotting and is widely used for

Table 3. Serum vs. nasal lavage levels of IL-13 in AR patients and healthy controls.

Group	Serum IL-13 (pg/mL)	Healthy vs. AR (serum), <i>p</i>	Nasal lavage IL-13 (pg/mL)	Healthy vs. AR (lavage), <i>p</i>	Serum vs. lavage (within group), <i>p</i>
Healthy controls	12.62 \pm 3.04	<0.001	12.84 \pm 2.93	<0.001	0.91
AR patients	67.62 \pm 2.25		75.24 \pm 2.34		0.024

the quantitative analysis of soluble proteins.

To evaluate the levels of IL-13 in the study subjects, ELISA assays were performed, stratifying samples by type (serum vs. nasal lavage). The levels of IL-13 (pg/mL) in both serum and nasal lavage fluid were compared between patients with AR and healthy controls. The results are summarized in Table 3.

The data in Table 3 show that IL-13 levels are significantly elevated in both serum and nasal lavage fluid of AR patients compared to healthy controls ($p < 0.001$). Fur-

Figure 1. Comparison of IL-13 levels in serum and nasal lavage fluid between healthy individuals and patients with AR. **A.** Comparison of serum IL-13 levels in healthy controls and AR patients. Elevated levels of IL-13 were found in the serum of AR patients compared to the control group ($p < 0.001$); **B.** Comparison of IL-13 levels in nasal lavage fluid in healthy individuals versus AR patients. IL-13 concentrations were significantly higher in the nasal lavage fluid of AR patients compared to healthy controls ($p < 0.01$).

thermore, within the AR group, IL-13 concentrations in nasal lavage were significantly higher than in serum ($p = 0.024$), suggesting a localized amplification of IL-13 expression in the upper airway mucosa. No significant difference was observed between serum and nasal IL-13 levels in the healthy control group ($p = 0.91$). These findings are graphically illustrated in Fig. 1.

No statistically significant difference was observed between serum IL-13 levels and those in nasal lavage fluid within the healthy control group ($p = 0.91$). Significantly higher levels of IL-13 were found in nasal lavage fluid compared to serum in patients with allergic rhinitis, as indicated in Fig. 2.

We chose to investigate this cytokine due to its critical role in initiating inflammatory responses, its responsibility in disrupting the integrity of the nasal epithelial barrier, and its central involvement in the pathogenesis of AR (Steelant et al. 2018; Nur Husna et al. 2022). Disruption of the epithelial barrier leads to the breakdown of intercellular junctions, resulting in increased epithelial permeability to various allergens (Capaldo and Nusrat 2009; Steelant et al. 2018). Furthermore, released cytokines hinder the reestablishment of epithelial integrity, thereby facilitating sustained contact with inflammatory allergens (London Jr et al. 2016).

We analyzed IL-13 levels in both peripheral blood (systemic level) and nasal lavage fluid (local level) to assess its differential effects on distinct anatomical sites within the respiratory tract. During the sensitization phase, antigen-presenting cells (APCs) take up allergens deposited on the mucosal surface, leading to the activation of antigen-specific T cells and the release of cytokines such as IL-13, which promotes the production of allergen-specific IgE antibodies. Upon re-exposure, the allergen binds to IgE on the surface of mast cells and circulating basophils, triggering their activation and the subsequent release of

histamine and leukotrienes (Sin and Togias 2011). These mediators contribute to the characteristic symptoms of AR by inducing airway hyperresponsiveness, mucus hypersecretion, vascular congestion, and nasal obstruction (Sahoo et al. 2016).

When we measured IL-13 protein concentrations in nasal lavage fluid from both healthy controls and AR patients, we observed significantly elevated levels of IL-13 in the patient group in both biological samples. This suggests that IL-13 is a reliable biomarker for distinguishing individuals with AR from healthy subjects. In healthy individuals, IL-13 concentrations were similar in serum and nasal lavage fluid, as expected, given that cytokine levels in this population are usually low. In contrast, IL-13 levels in nasal lavage fluid were significantly higher among patients with AR compared to levels in serum ($p = 0.024$). This finding supports the utility of both biological matrices for distinguishing between health and disease states. Furthermore, serum samples may be used to evaluate the systemic effects of IL-13, while nasal lavage provides insight into the local involvement of the nasal mucosa in the allergic inflammatory process. We aimed to determine the involvement of IL-13 in allergic inflammation by assessing its levels in patients with AR.

Our results showed a clear trend of elevated IL-13 levels in both serum and nasal lavage fluid among AR patients compared to healthy controls. Similar findings have been reported in the literature. For example, Nur Husna et al. (2022) reported significantly elevated serum IL-13 levels in AR patients compared to healthy individuals, and another study corroborated the increased systemic concentration of this cytokine (Nielsen et al. 2009). Additional studies have demonstrated increased nasal IL-13 levels, indicating that this marker may even help identify patients experiencing the late phase of the allergic response (Campion et al. 2023).

Figure 2. Comparison of IL-13 concentrations in serum and nasal lavage fluid between healthy individuals and patients with AR. **A.** Comparison of IL-13 concentrations in serum versus nasal lavage in healthy controls. No statistically significant difference was found between the two biological fluids in the healthy group ($p = 0.91$); **B.** Comparison of IL-13 concentrations in serum and nasal lavage fluid in patients with AR. Significantly elevated levels of IL-13 were observed in nasal lavage fluid compared to serum in the AR patient group.

It is plausible that cytokine profiles vary according to the specific type of allergen – a hypothesis that warrants further investigation. In the present study, we focused on quantifying IL-13 levels based solely on the type of biological material (serum or nasal lavage) to assess whether its expression is predominantly systemic or localized. IL-13 is implicated in various allergic responses, including airway hyperresponsiveness and mucus hypersecretion; therefore, its dysregulated expression constitutes a key element in the inflammatory response underlying allergic rhinitis.

Gene expression analysis of IL-13 in nasal lavage and serum samples from patients with AR and healthy controls

We aimed to determine whether the findings obtained from the ELISA analysis of IL-13 in nasal lavage and serum samples from patients with AR and healthy controls would be supported by evaluating the relative gene expression levels of the *IL13* gene. To this end, we performed real-time polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) in duplicate for each group. To minimize the risk of false or misleading results during these preliminary experiments, we included co-amplification of the housekeeping gene

Figure 3. Relative gene expression changes in IL-13 compared to the control group (initial results): serum levels in AR patients vs. healthy controls (** $p < 0.001$); and nasal lavage levels in AR patients vs. healthy controls (* $p < 0.01$). Data were normalized to *GAPDH* expression (control = healthy individuals; AR = allergic rhinitis patients).

GAPDH, which also served as an internal reference for normalizing expression data, thereby ensuring the accuracy of our results.

Our initial data demonstrated that, compared to healthy controls, the expression levels of *IL13* were significantly elevated in both serum and nasal lavage fluid of AR patients, reaching statistical significance.

IL-13 is a key Th2-type cytokine involved in the pathogenesis of allergic airway diseases, including allergic rhinitis. According to published literature, elevated mRNA

expression levels of IL-13 have been detected in the nasal mucosa, peripheral blood, and lavage fluids of AR patients, reflecting the activation of Th2-mediated immune responses to environmental allergens. IL-13 promotes eosinophilic infiltration, mucus hypersecretion, and epithelial remodeling, all of which contribute to the characteristic symptoms of rhinitis, such as nasal obstruction and rhinorrhea (Pawankar et al. 1995). Notably, low-level IL-13 expression can also be detected in healthy individuals, suggesting a baseline homeostatic role in mucosal immunity that is amplified upon allergen exposure (Dalessandri et al. 2016). The observed differential expression between patients and controls highlights the potential utility of IL-13 as a diagnostic or therapeutic biomarker of allergic inflammation (Wang et al. 2023).

Understanding the biological characteristics of IL-13, its signaling pathways, and therapeutic antibodies is expected to advance diagnostic precision, enable personalized treatment strategies, and improve disease prognosis. Clinical trials targeting IL-13 in AR have not yet yielded the expected clinical outcomes. Studies are ongoing, as several new agents under investigation have demonstrated improvements in pulmonary function but not in disease symptoms. In a randomized, double-blind trial (NCT06523478) employing a nasal allergen challenge model, data showed that anti-IL-13 had specific pharmacodynamic activity, causing strong inhibition of IL-13 responses in nasal mucosal fluid but no improvement in overall nasal symptoms or eosinophilic infiltration (Nicholson et al. 2011).

IL-13 is certainly involved in late-phase allergic responses (Campion et al. 2023), a feature that complicates its therapeutic modulation. More recently, lebrikizumab has demonstrated promising effects in persistent or perennial allergic rhinitis, although the data remain limited (NCT06339008). In recent years, multiple clinical trials have been conducted to evaluate its safety, pharmacokinetics, and efficacy, especially in dermatological and respiratory conditions (Blauvelt et al. 2023; Silverberg et al. 2023).

Clinically, selective blockade of IL-13 has yielded inconsistent benefits in AR, whereas dupilumab (anti-IL-4R α ; dual IL-4/IL-13 inhibition) shows a clearer – though context-dependent – signal (Castro et al. 2018; Weinstein et al. 2018). In patients with moderate to severe asthma and perennial AR, dupilumab improves rhinitis-related and rhinoconjunctivitis-specific scores while suppressing type 2 biomarkers and allergen-specific IgE.

Selective inhibition of IL-13 has shown promising results, although symptomatic benefit has been modest and heterogeneous to date. In contrast, dual blockade of IL-4 and IL-13 signaling by inhibiting IL-4R α (e.g., dupilumab) more comprehensively suppresses type 2 cytokine pathways, resulting in broader and more consistent clinical efficacy in respiratory and dermatological indications. Direct comparisons are not yet available; therefore, future studies should consider stratification by IL-13-high phenotype and explore combination approaches for more optimized clinical outcomes.

There are several limitations to our study, including the small sample size and the preliminary nature of these experiments evaluating the gene expression of this interleukin. Additionally, the SYBR Green–based qPCR kit used in this study is known to exhibit limitations in the specificity of amplification signals, which may result in false-positive outcomes. Thus, our findings are not yet conclusive and require further replication, validation, and improved experimental reproducibility. In future experiments, we plan to employ TaqMan probe–based assays, which offer enhanced specificity due to sequence-specific hybridization to the target region, to validate and confirm our preliminary results.

Conclusion

IL-13 is an immunoregulatory cytokine predominantly secreted by activated Th2 cells. There is increasing evidence that IL-13 is a key mediator in the pathology and development of allergic inflammation. It shares numerous functional features with IL-4, largely attributed to their common receptor subunit, IL-4R α . Although findings in the literature remain somewhat inconsistent, there is strong overall support for the role of IL-13 as a major driver of allergic inflammatory responses.

The *IL13* gene is actively expressed, and IL-13 levels are elevated in the nasal mucosa of individuals with allergic rhinitis; however, its exact role in the development and progression of AR remains unclear. Further investigation into the biological properties of IL-13, including its signaling pathways and expression patterns, may facilitate more accurate diagnostics and improved therapeutic strategies for this condition.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors’ representatives: Clinic of Allergology, University Hospital “Alexandrovska”

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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